

SAIBAGE

Sulfur-Aluminium Battery with Advanced Polymeric Gel Electrolytes

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Special course on Novelty battery systems

Project partners

LOGO	Partner full name	Acronym
	Albufera Energy Storage S.L.	AES
	University of Leicester	UoL
	Scionix Ltd.	Scionix
	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	CSIC
	Technische Universität Graz	TUG
	University of Southampton	UoS
	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet	DTU

Deliverable Name: *Special course on Novelty battery systems*

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R	PU	Special course on Novelty battery systems	D.1.4-PU-04-2019	01/00	04/10/2019	2 / 5

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1. Scope of the JESS 2019 Summer School

The increase in energy production from renewable sources creates a demand for energy storage technologies. Storage and conversion can be accomplished electrochemically: in batteries or through electrolysis and fuel cells. Therefore, these technologies are poised to play a major role in the energy supply infrastructure of the near future.

The Joint European Summer School JESS 2019 addressed these issues by offering high quality graduate level courses on selected topics of fuel cells, electrolyser, and battery technologies. This series of summer schools has been ongoing since 2004 and targets an audience of university students (MSc and PhD levels), and post-doctoral researchers. We also welcome more experienced researchers and engineers wishing to review these technologies and expand their general knowledge, for instance, to suit a newly acquired position or collect credits for a Continuous Professional Development (CPD) scheme. The topical content is tailored to the needs of a diverse audience: newcomers to the field, experienced students, and young professionals working at the forefront of fuel cell, electrolyser, and battery applications.

The school is internally advertised among the students at DTU and at all the universities involved in the organization of the school (University of Birmingham, Ulster University, and Forschungszentrum Jülich). The school is also externally advertised among more than 50 research groups in Europe and also through the school webpage (<http://www.iess-summer-school.eu/>)

The school is used as a framework to present and disseminate the methods and results of the different projects, including SALBAGE, in which the organizers are involved. The school is sponsored by several companies involved in battery research such as Toyota, Elcogen, Heatstack, and Sunfire.

2. Batteries at the JESS 2019 Summer School

Concerning batteries, our involvement in the JESS Summer School has been to introduce the students to various theoretical frameworks, from an introduction to computational models and high-throughput screening for novel materials, to modelling in batteries and interfaces. More in details, we have provided:

- A theoretical descriptions of the fundamental mechanisms and properties of lithium-ion, and metal-sulphur, e.g. specific energies and over-voltages.
- Materials demands for the individual components, i.e. the electrolyte material, the anode material and the cathode material in Li-ion and metal-sulphur batteries.
- Description of the ionic liquids as electrolytes using as an example the AlCl₃-urea liquid in Salbage.
- Description of pros and cons of polymer electrolytes vs. conventional electrolytes.
- Electrochemical characterization and evaluation of cell properties by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy methods.
- Description/studies of degradation mechanisms.

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- Safety issues.

For the first time in the history of the JESS Summer School, we have included more detailed explanation of the mechanisms of batteries based on sulphur, of which AIS is a particular case.

3. Students of the JESS 2019

Figure 2: Adsorption energy of an Al-atom on co-doped surfaces (Zn+ Ga, In, or Bi) and pristine Al. The adsorption sites are indicated in the figure on the right.

4. References

- (1) <http://www.jess-summerschool.eu/week-1>
- (2) <https://kurser.dtu.dk/course/47508>

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